

PERCEPTIONS OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS ON THE PRACTICES OF EDUCATIONAL QUALITY ENHANCEMENT IN DILLA UNIVERSITY: A CORRELATION STUDY

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Abstract:

The development and practices of enhancing quality in higher education is one of the areas of the ongoing debate. Quality of education and its enhancement come at the forefront of all crucial issues in the context of increasing recognition of the role of higher education for national development. Universities in general, become complex in terms of expanding access and study programs and they depend on government for their full financial resources. These trends raise a concern about quality of education and thus lead to demand for accountability on the part of university. The study, being a descriptive survey, used both qualitative and quantitative approaches to data collection with a view to investigate the perception of teachers and students on the practices of educational quality enhancement in Dilla University. The use of the qualitative approach substantiated the investigators to develop an understanding of individuals and events in their natural settings.

Keywords: quality enhancement in education, perception on quality enhancement, practices of educational quality enhancement

1. Introduction

It is imperative to understand that the formal quality enhancement in higher education has now become one of the central components of reform and policy instruments to adapt higher education institutions to the increasing expectations from both internal and external stakeholders all over the world. As Reichert (2008) puts it, quality

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enhancement is so widespread and its vocabulary is so pervasive, nowadays in higher education policy and discourse that one forgets how relatively recent the enthronement of the term “quality” actually is. The quality revolution in higher education has underscored the expectation that universities must demonstrate that they are providing quality education and strives to improve it (Anderson, 2006).

Dilla University is one of the newly established public higher learning institutions as per the higher education proclamation number of 238. The institution, as a newly emerged institution is currently undertaking a wide ranges of infrastructural and academic activities in all of its campuses. Despite the fact that the university registered more no. of students in a regular, week end and summer program basis and regulates a smooth teaching and learning process, a certain number of scholars and academicians of the institute critiques the practices of educational quality enhancement. Hence, this study focused on teachers’ and students’ perception on the practices of educational quality enhancement in Dilla University.

2. Statement of the Problem

The development and practices of enhancing quality in higher education is one of the areas of ongoing debate. Quality of education and its enhancement come at the forefront of all crucial issues in the context of increasing recognition of the role of higher education for national development. How universities demonstrate quality of their education in a changing higher education environment requires an understanding of their current practices and systems for assuring quality based on empirical research (Mulu, 2012). The practice of enhancing quality at university level is a recent phenomenon. More importantly, it is not well researched and documented in the context of developing regions like Ethiopia in general and Dilla University in particular. In the Ethiopian context, research on higher education in general and on quality assurance in particular is inadequate. A review of some of the books written on Ethiopian higher education (Teshome, 1990; Teshome, 2007; Amare, 2007) indicates that none of them had a focus on quality concern in higher education.

There has been an environmental change in the Ethiopian higher education landscape. The environmental changes could be illustrated by: a rapid institutional and enrolment expansion amid financial stringency, frequent changes in policy directions, perceived decline in quality of education, etc. The university is becoming complex in terms of expanding access and study programs and it depend on government for their full financial resources. These trends raise a concern about quality of education and thus lead to demand for accountability on the part of university. Under these circumstances this study entitled “Perceptions of Teachers and Students on the Practices of Educational Quality Enhancement in Dilla University: A Correlation Study” assumes importance.

2.1 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are stated as follows:

- To disclose the possible factors those enable and/or hinder the adoption and practices of educational quality enhancement.
- To determine whether a significant relationship is observed between the perceptions of teachers and students on the practices of educational quality enhancement.
- To propose possible solutions that may help to improve educational quality enhancement.

2.2 Significances of the Study

The study may have the following importance;

- The findings of the study can be availed to develop theoretical framework for building quality assurance systems that fit to the context of Ethiopian universities.
- The study may provide pertinent information concerning the existing systems and practices of assuring quality to the Ethiopian public universities,
- The study may raise the awareness of key stakeholders regarding the problems in the development and implementation of quality assurance.
- The policy makers involved in the planning, management and improvement of the higher education system in Ethiopia would be benefitted of the findings of the study.

2.3 Delimitation of the Study

Even though there are a number of educational issues needed to be investigated within the institution, this study is delimited only to the perceptions of teachers and students on practices of educational quality enhancement in Dilla University with special reference to the quality of teaching and learning process. Considering the said justification, the scope of the study has been limited to the perceptions of teachers and students on practices of educational quality enhancement in Dilla University.

2.4 Limitations of the Study

The study had the limitations of survey type research such as clarity of wording and respondent understanding of terminology. The survey was administered to a limited sample and hence the findings are also limited to the public universities

2.5 Operational Definition of Terms

Higher Education is a post-secondary learning institution which is may be established by law or accredited by an authorized agency. Examples are universities and colleges For the purpose of this study, the following basic terms are used.

Perception: In this study, it refers on how teachers and students view and understand the practices of educational quality enhancement in Dilla University.

Quality: refers to something that fits a purpose.

Quality Enhancement is taking deliberate steps to bring about improvement in the effectiveness of the learning experiences of students.

3. Review of Related Literature

3.1 Concept of Quality in Education

Sanjara (2006), explained quality as a much debated term which some views like 'beauty' that lies in the eye of the beholder. The one who believe on this are '*relativists*', whereas, these who believe that quality can be a specific attributes which can be identified, they are '*objectivists*'. Besides, the British Standard Institution (BSI, 1991) as cited in Sanjara (2006), defines quality as "*the totality of features and characteristics of a product or service to satisfy stated or implied needs*".

Westerheijden (1999) was of the view that quality in educational setting is evidence for conformity with institutional missions as well as capacity to fulfilling customers' requirements is the principal perspective underlying this. The interpretation of quality as fitness of purpose is linked to the adequacy of the quality related intentions of an organization, which provides a check on fitness for purpose.

3.2 Quality Enhancement in Higher Education

Carley and Waldron (1984) defined quality enhancement in education as planned, deliberate activities instigated and carried out with the intent and purpose of maintaining and improving the quality of learning for participants. Harvey & Green (1993), refer it as "*Those mechanisms and procedures designed to reassure various 'stakeholders' in higher education that institutions accord a high priority to implementing policies designed to maintain and enhance institutional effectiveness*".

Quality in higher education is a multidimensional concept, which includes all the related functions and activities that form part of the academic life in a university system. Therefore, any framework for the assessment of quality should take into account the quality of students, teachers, infrastructure, student support services, curricula, assessment and learning resources (Muhammad *et al*, 2011).

3.3 Indicators of Quality Enhancement in Higher Education

There are a range of statistical and non-statistical indicators intended to offer an objective measure of how a given higher education institution is performing its tasks. Some of the indicators are: Users satisfaction, Use of entry qualification, Student retention, Learning / teaching output, Research, Graduate employment, Change in attitude of the students. (Chande, 2006)

Murnane (1987) was of the view that quality indicators, specifically in higher learning institutions can be divided into three classes: These are consisting of;

- 1) Educational inputs;
- 2) Educational outputs, and

3) Educational processes.

Inputs include financial measures, physical measures, and manpower measures associated with the resources that are provided for students. Financial measures are generally summarized by educational expenditures per student. Physical measures include the age, condition, and comprehensiveness of such facilities as classrooms, laboratories, and libraries and the provision and use of international materials and equipment. Manpower or human resource measures include the number of personnel of different types, often expressed as ratios in relation to student numbers at each level. They also include background information about these personnel such as educational qualifications, experience, and perhaps knowledge competencies and attitudes (Murnane, 1987).

Harvey and Green (1993) identify five different approaches in measuring quality in higher education. These include:

- In term of the exceptional (higher standards);
- In terms of consistency (zero defects and getting it right the first time);
- As fitness for purpose (meeting stated purposes);
- As value for money, and
- As transformative (transformation of the participant)

The current situation enjoys the benefit of nearly four decades of thinking in this regard, including the various conflicting approaches about whether attention should be given only to the output or whether both the inputs and the throughput should be taken into consideration. The current thinking appears to favor a distinction between Quality Audit and Quality Assessment (Harvey & Green, 1993).

3.4 Overview of Ethiopian higher Education System

Though Ethiopia possesses a 1,700-year tradition of elite education linked to the Orthodox Church, secular higher education was initiated only in 1950 with the founding of the University College of Addis Ababa and half a dozen specialized technical colleges were established during the following two decades (Saint W., 2004). These institutions hosted an educational culture that was heavily influenced by its long informal association with the Orthodox Church (Teshome 1990). As Saint W. (2004) indicated that their academic organization was somewhat more American and less British than higher education systems in the former British colonies of East Africa. Strikingly, tertiary enrolments totaled only 4,500 in 1970 out of a national population of 34 million. The resulting tertiary enrolment ratio of 0.2 per cent was among the very lowest in the world. The skilled human resources available to guide development in one of Africa's largest and poorest countries were therefore miniscule in relation to the enormity of the task (Teshome, 1990). The nation's new higher education institutions strove, with considerable early success, to maintain international standards. But the cost was high, with wastage rates approaching 40 per cent in the late 1960s (Teshome 1990 as cited in Saint, 2004). Awareness of the need for reform began to grow.

3.5 Quality Enhancement in Ethiopian Public Higher Education System

In Ethiopia, the idea that enhancement of quality education is necessary and should be developed through an Agency came from the Government and is enshrined in the 2003 Higher Education Proclamation (Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2003). According to Ashcroft (2012), the requirement for the establishment is to monitor for accreditation purposes (especially important in regulating the expanding private sector) and also to ensure that quality does not suffer to an unknowable extent: such a rapid expansion puts pressure on the limited pool of capable and qualified people and systems to manage the institutions. At the same time, Government cannot micro-manage such a diverse and large system (as it has done in the past) and so must balance central control with institutional autonomy. It has changed the operation of power within Government and devolved considerable freedoms and responsibilities to the universities. It has looked to the northern developed countries for ways to manage this and has used concepts of quality and quality assurance, operated through quasi-autonomous sector support units, as the basis for a relatively “hands-off” system of regulation and control. Recognizing the importance of quality and relevance in this new context, the 2003 Higher Education Proclamation established HERQA.

It was hoped that this organization would mitigate political risks by showing that the newly expanded system is “producing quality” whilst at the same time providing many more students with the opportunity for post-secondary education, increasing the level of skills and professionalism amongst the population and helping to meet the country’s development needs.

Besides, of the establishment of HERQA at central level, every state owned higher learning institution in Ethiopia is currently undertaking a variety of activities to enhance educational quality and improve students’ learning through opening an integrated office called quality enhancement/quality audit/ office at institution level.

3.6 Factors that Enable or Hinder the Practice of Educational Quality Enhancement in Public Universities

Mulu (2012) explained them as follows;

“Factors related to university characteristics refer to those elements that differentiate one university from the other. On the other hand, environmental factors are those factors within the domain of the task and institutional environment of the universities. The organizational environmental factors are common to all universities.”

4. Research Methodology

This section covers the description of the study area, research design, sources of data, population and sample, data collection instruments, procedures of data collection, methods of data analysis and ethical considerations.

4.1 Description of the Study Area

Dilla University is situated at Gedeo zone of Dilla, 360 Kms south wards of Addis Ababa, the capital city of Ethiopia. At the first, it was established as the College of Teachers' Education and Health Sciences in 1996. Later, it was converted into a part of Debub University. Consequently, it was established as full-fledged university as per the Councils of Ministers' Regulation Number of 129/2004 in 2004. Subsequently, it was re-established by the Councils of Ministers as per the Regulation No of 238/2011.

Besides undertaking a variety of outreaching activities with a view to achieve its vision of being one among the most top ten universities in east African in the areas of teaching and learning, the University started research, consulting and community services. The University is consisted of six colleges, two institutes and two schools and a number of academic programs in both under and post graduate studies.

4.2 Research Design

The study, being a descriptive survey, used both qualitative and quantitative approaches to data collection with a view to investigate the perception of teachers and students on the practices of educational quality enhancement in Dilla University. The use of the qualitative approach substantiated the investigators to develop an understanding of individuals and events in their natural settings.

4.3 Data Sources

Both primary and secondary sources of data were availed in the study. The primary data were collected from the academic staff, students, Director for Quality Enhancement Office and college the Deans of the University. With regard to the secondary data, documents were analyzed.

4.4 Population of the Study

The target population of the study was Dilla university's academic employees, students and academic officials for the simple reason that the academic staffs are the most important people to run the core business of the institution. Moreover, the extent to which whether educational quality is improved depends on them. Also, the students who are the good judges to say whether quality teaching is taken place are most indispensable for the study.

4.5 Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

From the whole of the University, three colleges viz. the Colleges of Engineering and Technology, Business & Economics and the College of Health and Medical Science were selected as the sample adopting simple random sampling technique. From these colleges 70 (about 43%) of the academics currently working in the university were included under the sample size besides the Director for Quality Enhancement Office, two college Deans and 116 second and above year students were included in the sample size of the study. Teachers from each college were selected by availing stratified

sampling method. Whereas, students were selected randomly adopting simple random sampling techniques. But, at the same time, the Director for Quality Enhancement Office, and college were drawn as a sample availing purposive sampling method to include them in sample size intentionally as both of them were indispensable for the study.

4.6 Instruments of Data Collection and Procedures

The following tools were used to collect the required data for the study:

A. Questionnaire

In this study, a survey questionnaire was availed in collecting the quantitative data. The questionnaire consisted of 31 items was administered to 116 students and 70 teachers to elicit their perceptions towards the practices of educational quality enhancement in the University. The respondents were requested to indicate their perceptions on a five-point Likert type scale to indicate their level of agreement with each item. An opportunity for free responses was also provided at the end of the questionnaire. Comments were analysed to enhance the presentation of data with a view to complement the discussion of the findings.

B. Validity and Reliability

Validity refers the extent to which the research instrument measures what it is supposed to measure (Haber & Lobiondo-Wood 2006). Besides, (AERA, APA, NCME, 1999) as cited in (Creswell, 2008) defined validity as it is the development of sound evidence to demonstrate that the test interpretation (of scores about the concept or construct that the test is assumed to measure) matches its proposed use. On the other hand, the reliability of the research instrument is the extent to which the instrument yields the same results on repeated measures (Haber & Lobiondo-Wood 2006).

The researchers pilot tested the instrument and applied Alpha coefficient to ascertain the internal consistency of the questionnaire towards establishing the validity of the tool. The instrument was administered to 20 teachers and 50 students randomly selected from the university outside of the selected sample colleges. The aim of the pilot study was to test the appropriateness of the instruments being used besides finding out whether additions or modifications are important on the basis of the pre-test experience. The reliability of the questionnaire was confirmed by examining the individual test items using the Cronbach's alpha (Gall et al., 2007; Bryman & Cramer, 2009, 363). The internal reliability alpha coefficients were calculated to be 0.838 revealing that the research instrument was reliable.

C. Interview, Observation and Documents Analysis

In order to improve the trustworthiness of data, researchers suggest the use of multiple data-collection methods or what they call "triangulation" process (Gall et al., 2007; Bogdan & Biklen, 2007). Triangulation process not only helps the researchers to increase the credibility and validity of their study but also to eliminate biases that may result from relying exclusively on any one data-collection method, source, analyst or theory. In this direction, the study employed interview, observation and documents analysis as

a second method to supplement, authenticate and/or clarify issues raised in the questionnaire responses. Individual interviews were also administered to a sample of 2 college Deans and the Director for Academic Quality Audit in Amharic language regarding the current practices of educational quality enhancement. Besides, observation was also carried out and different documents were analyzed.

4.7 Procedures of Data Collection

Having reviewed the related literature, the researchers, the research strategy was finalized followed by selecting three colleges from the university. Subsequently, the interview schedules and questionnaire were compiled, pilot tested and reviewed. The researchers administered the questionnaire and conducted interviews with the respondents followed by data tabulation and analysis.

4.8 Methods of Data Analysis

The researcher availed both quantitative and qualitative methods for data analysis. The data was analyzed quantitatively by using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency, means, standard deviations and independent sample test were applied to analyze items in the survey. But, at the same time, the responses of open ended questions, interview, observation and the results of document analysis were qualitatively analyzed by using of descriptive terms.

Correlations were also attempted with a view to see the relationships between teachers' perception with that of students' regarding the practices to enhance educational quality as well as the relationships of these scales with perceived standards to educational quality enhancement. In the same manner, independent sample t-test was used to analyze whether differences were found between the perception of instructors and students with respect to the issue under investigation.

4.9 Ethical Considerations

Consent of the respondents was obtained by the researchers and that their participation was indeed voluntary. Care was taken to see that anonymity and confidentiality was assured to the respondents. After the completion of the interviews, participants had given opportunity to review their responses with a view to make any changes to their statements.

5. Data Analyses, Interpretation and Discussion of Results

This section presents the results of statistical analyses undertaken in order to answer the major research questions raised in the study.

5.1 Biographic Information of Respondents

The Table: 1 provides a descriptive picture of the biographic information of the teachers and students of Dilla University who became the sample of the study.

Table 1: Biographic Information of Respondents

S.No	Category	Alternative	Subjects				Total	
			Teachers		Students		N	%
			N	%	N	%		
1	College	Engineering and Technology	34	56.7	52	49.5	86	52.1
		Business and Economics	16	26.7	24	22.9	40	24.2
		Health and Medicine	10	16.6	29	27.6	39	23.7
		Total	60	100	105	100	165	100
2	Sex	Male	48	80	59	56.2	107	64.9
		Female	12	20	46	43.8	58	35.1
		Total	60	100	105	100	165	100

From the Table: 1, it is noted that 34(56.7%) of the teacher respondents were from College of Engineering and Technology and 16(26.7%) of them were from college of Business and Economics. Whereas, the rest 10(16.6) of the teacher respondents were from the College of Health and Medical science. Concerning sex of teacher respondents, about 80% of them were males and the remaining 12(20%) were female. This indicates there is still low participation of female instructors in HLI. Regarding student respondents characteristics, it is found that 52(49.5%) of the student respondents were from College of Engineering and Technology (E&T) and 24(22.9%), 29(27.6%) of the respondents were from the Colleges of Business and Economics and Health& Medical Sciences. Regarding the gender of the respondents, 59(56.2%) of them were male while the remaining 46(43.8%) of them were female student respondents.

5.2 Impacts of Some External Factors on Enhancing Quality of Education

The impacts of some external factors on enhancing the quality of education have been presented in the Table 2.

Table 2: Impacts of Some External Factors on Quality of Education

S. No	Variables	Respondents (N=165)						Sig (2-tailed)	t-value
		Teachers			Students				
		N	$\bar{X}$	SD _{tea}	N	$\bar{X}$	SD _{stu}		
1	Government Intervention in Internal Affairs of Institutions	60	2.84	1.06	105	2.69	1.32	.138	-1.526
2	Political Stability	60	4.94	.97	105	4.80	.95	.573	-.571
3	Economic Stability	60	4.00	1.00	105	4.46	1.10	.077	1.842
4	Technological Advancement	60	4.47	.76	105	3.96	1.03	.069	1.884

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5	External Quality Regulation (HERQA) Requirements and Expectations	60	4.36	1.21	105	4.94	.959	.063	1.959
6	Higher Education Law	60	4.26	1.04	105	4.29	1.07	.903	.123
7	Institutional and Student Enrolment Expansion Policy	60	4.89	.73	105	4.31	1.12	.055	1.985
8	Preparation of Incoming Students	60	4.64	.77	105	4.08	1.13	.515	.657
9	Students socio Economic Background	60	4.36	.89	105	4.32	1.12	.818	-.233

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

.t-table=1.96 df =163

It is found from the Table: 3, that the mean value ($x=2.84$ and 2.69 of teachers and students respectively) for item1 indicates that teachers and students perception towards the impact/contribution of government intervention to educational quality is low. On the other hand, the mean scores ($x=4.94$ and 4.80 for item 2), ($x=4.00$ and 4.46 for item 3), ($x= 4.47$ and 3.96 for item 4), ($x= 4.36$ and 4.94 for item 5), ($x= 4.26$ and 4.29 for item 6), ($x= 4.89$ and 4.31 for item 7), ($x=4.64$ and 4.08 for item 8) and ($x= 4.36$ and 4.32 for item 9) of teachers and students response respectively showed that their perception towards the impacts/contributions of political stability, economic stability, technological advancement, regulatory, higher education law, institutional and students enrollment and expansion policy, preparation of incoming students and students socio economic background high in improving the educational quality. The t-test values ($t=-.152, -.57, 1.84, 1.88, 1.95, .12, 1.98, .65,$ and $-.23$ where t_{-table} is 1.96) also indicate that there were no statistically significance variations in the responses of both teachers and their counterparts at $P<.05$ level of significance relationship of 163 df. As the mean values indicate that respondents of both group rated the contribution/impact of government intervention for enhancement of quality of education as low. All mentioned variable other the first one, were rated as a contributing factors to the process of educational quality enhancement.

An interview session was also conducted with concerned bodies to substantiate the findings. Therefore, the results of the interview and open ended questionnaire authenticated that students must be inclined to their talents and should well be guided/prepared at preparatory level so that they can proceed with higher education without any difficulty. It is also found from the open ended questions and interview that factors like political stability, economic growth, technological advancement and socio economic background of students are among the determinant factors for the improvement of educational quality. From this, it is possible to infer that the contribution of external factors to enhance educational quality is relied to be high. In addition, it shows that educational quality enhancement is highly dependent on some external factors to succeed or failed.

5.3 Correlation Analysis of the Variables in the Study

The results of the correlation analyses of the variables studies have been presented in the Table: 3.

Table 3: Inter Correlation between Respondents and the Variables Treated in the Study

S. No	Variables	Correlations with subjects(respondents)
1	Role of different stakeholders in enhancing educational quality	0.07
2	Level of Satisfaction of respondents with practices of DU	-0.215*
3	Quality and access of Infrastructure, facilities and learning resources	-0.149*
4	Level of students commitment and Engagement in promoting educational quality	-0.210*
5	Impact/contributions external factors to enhance educational quality	0.060

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

From the Table: 4, it is found that there was not statistically significant relationship between subjects and variable 1 ($r=.07$); subjects and variable 5 ($r= .06$); whereas, there was statistically significant relationship between subjects and level of satisfaction of respondents with current practices of the university in enhancing educational quality ($r=-.215$), subjects and quality of infrastructure ($r=-.149$) and subjects with the level of students commitment and engagement in enhancing educational quality ($r= -.210$) at ($P= 0.05$).

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers forwarded the following recommendations:

- All colleges, schools, institutes and departments should develop a minimum learning requirements of all courses offered and assess students based on those competencies.
- Improve the library space and stock, particularly reference books, text books, academic periodicals and digital resources for all campuses.
- Improve the ICT centers and internet access for all staff and students through providing broadband and Wi-Fi internet access around students' dormitories, offices, recreational areas, libraries and classrooms.
- Improve the conditions of toilets, water and power supply, sport fields, and lounges to the extent of no complaints can be raised by students and staff.
- Create a strong chain of communication with all stakeholders both in and out of the nation so that to create a positive and partnership linkage.

7. Conclusion

The current educational quality enhancement practices in Dilla university are found to be inadequate in facilitating an improved teaching and learning process. Some underlying reasons mentioned by respondents include lack of inputs/learning resources, commitment and quality of both teachers and students of the university. Regarding the roles of different internal stakeholders in enhancing the quality of education, majority of respondents felt that their contribution as important. They specially rated the degree of roles of top management's contribution as high. With respect to level of satisfaction of respondents and degree of significances of some practices in promoting educational quality, majority of respondents expressed that as their level of satisfaction and degree of significance in enhancing quality of education with regard to cooperative learning was high. Whereas, the feeling of both respondents concerning leadership commitment to promote educational quality was low. However, both respondents level of satisfaction varied on the academic staff commitment and qualification, assessment mechanisms, staff and students' recruitment and development practices of the university. Teachers had showed higher level of agreement on overall the of the practices related items in the survey. Whereas students rated the commitment and quality of teachers, class rooms, assessment mechanisms, staff and students' recruitment and development practices of the university as poor practice. Moreover, the aggregated result indicates that teachers significantly differed on overall attitudes towards their level of satisfaction and degree of significances of current practices in enhancing quality of education. Respondents advocated that the quality and access of infrastructure, facilities and learning resources was lowly practiced. They also differed with regard to students' commitment and engagement level and by most teachers rated as low. Regarding the impacts of external factors, the respondents agreed that the contributions of the external factors like political and economic stability, technological advancement, HERQA regulator, HEL, preparation of students and socio economic background of students were high.

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